

Türk Siyasal Hayatında 'Özde' ve 'Sözde' Demokratikleşme: 1980 Sonrasının Değerlendirilmesi

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Özet

Bu çalışmanın amacı, özde ve sözde demokratikleşme kavramlarının temel dayanaklarının irdelenmesi, Türk siyasi tarihinde bu kavramlara tesir eden süreçlerin araştırılmasıdır. Çalışma öncelikle Türk siyasi yaşamında anayasal süreçlerle gelişim gösteren demokrasi ve demokratikleşme süreçleri üzerinde durmuştur. Özde ve sözde demokrasi kavramları irdelenerek, hukuki metinlerde demokratik bir hak olarak karşımıza çıkan 'özde demokrasi' kavramı ile uygulamada bir şekilde ihlal edilen bu hakkın ortaya çıkmış hali olan 'sözde demokrasi' kavramlarının demokrasi kültürüne etkisi incelenmiştir. Türkiye'de tek partili yaşam ve takiben darbe dönemleri köklü bir demokrasi geleneğinin yerleşmesinin önünde ciddi engeller olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır. Bu durum başta demokrasinin sakıncalı bir hal almasına ve anayasal metinlere bu şekilde yansımaya sebep olmuştur. Bununla birlikte özellikle çalışmanın çerçevesini oluşturan 1980 sonrası dönemde anayasal metinlerde bir şekilde yer verilmiş olan bir takım hak ve özgürlüklerin bazı gerekçelerle sınırlandırılması için iyice demokratik özünden koparılmasına sebep olmaktadır. Demokrasi ve insan hakları ölçeğinde değerlendirildiğinde özünden koparılmış bir hak ve özgürlük alanından söz edebilecek duruma geldiğimizde ise artık özde demokrasi yerini sözde bir demokratik anlayışa bırakmış olacaktır. Bu çalışma 1980 sonrası dönemde özellikle 1982 anayasasının yapılış süreci ve anayasa metninde bulunan bazı özgürlüklerin uygulama alanında ne denli sorunlarla ve çelişkilerle karşılaştığını, pratikte bunları aşmak için hangi yol ve yöntemlerin uygulandığı üzerinde durmaktadır.

Genuine Democratization And Pseudo Democratization İn Turkish Political Life: An Evaluation Of The Post-1980 Period

Keywords:

constitution, human rights, genuine democracy, pseudo democracy.

Abstract

This study aimed to examine the basic foundations of the concepts of genuine democratization and pseudo democratization and investigate the processes affecting these concepts in Turkish political history. The study first focused on democracy and democratization processes that have developed through the constitutional structure in Turkish political life. Next, it examined the concepts of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy and analyzed the first as a human right in constitutional texts and the latter as that which has emerged as a violation in the practice of the former against the culture of democracy. Single-party democracy and subsequent coup periods in Turkey have been serious obstacles to the establishment of a deep-rooted democratic tradition. Democracy has become objectionable and is reflected in this way in constitutional texts. Several rights and freedoms that are enshrined in constitutional texts were restricted on certain grounds, especially in the post-1980 period that constituted the framework of this study, which has led to a detachment from genuine democracy. When the ideal of rights and freedoms is detached from the practice of democracy and human rights, genuine democracy will have been replaced by a pseudo democracy. This study focused on the problems and contradictions that were encountered in the post-1980 period, especially in the process of drafting the 1982 Constitution and in the implementation of some freedoms included in the text of the constitution, and the ways and methods used to overcome them in practice.

1. INTRODUCTION

Democracy is a finite and infinite concept in its various forms, which is emphasized in particular by political scientists (Türk, 2017: 19). There have been many discussions on democracy due to its multiple structures. Democracy has been shaped both as a value-laden concept and as a normative form of political administration (Türk, 2017: 20). According to Rousseau, who emphasized that true democracy would never exist, the fact that the majority rules and the minority is ruled is contrary to the natural order, and it is not possible for the people to come together and vote for public affairs (Rousseau, 1982: 80). Indeed, The concentration of all political authority in the centre is not appropriate for a pluralistic democracy (Yılmaz & Telsaç, 2021: 238). As an outcome of this perspective, it is emphasized that pure democracy has been sacrificed to representative democracy. The fact that affairs are carried out through representatives has made the practice of democracy in its pure form almost impossible. The fact that the personal situation of the representatives has come into play, along with their will and ambitions, has detached democracy from its essence and given it a pseudo meaning. Rousseau again emphasized the impossibility of ideal democracy in his Social Contract theory: “If the gods had a nation, it would be governed by democracy; humans cannot build such a perfect system” (Zabunoğlu, 2017: 796). It is difficult for democracy to be applied in its pure form, thus rendering pure democracy obsolete. Alternative forms and methods have led to the emergence of various forms of democracy and the shaping of the relationship between the ruler and the ruled through these forms. Different versions of democracy are generally accepted; however, there is no broad consensus. It is noteworthy that there are deep differences in its use in intellectual and practical fields (Karadaş, 2020: 125). The concept of democracy contains several contradictions that arise from factors such as the tension between majority rule and minority rights, the balance between freedom and security, and equality and economic inequalities. (Tocqueville, 2016: 217) warns that “the pressure of the majority tends to violate the rights of minorities,” emphasizing the contradictions of this aspect of democracy. The fact that the majority forms the basis of the decision-making mechanism paves the way for minority rights to be ignored. One of the paradoxes of democracy emerges from establishing a balance between liberty and security. Especially in times of crisis, democratic governments often seek to ensure security by restricting individual liberties. (Mill, 2001: 31) discusses this balance, stating, “The restriction of individual liberties should be not only for security but also for the general good of society.” However, this situation raises the possibility of restricting freedoms for the sake of security, which contradicts the fundamental characteristics of democracy. Again, considering that democracy consists only of political equality leads to a contradiction in formulating it in this way; the inequality that arises in the economy cannot make political equality meaningful. Populist discourses and leaders can lead to another contradiction for democracy: “Populism often aims to create a centralized power and deepen social polarization rather than reflecting the will of the people” (Mudde & Kaltwasser, 2017: 80–81). Herein, leaders often claim that they defend the rights of the majority, but this can harm pluralism and minority rights. Countries claiming to be strictly committed to democratic values may sometimes establish relationships with authoritarian structures in line with their interests for the sake of sacrificing democratic values, leading to the emergence of a democracy-authority relationship, which becomes another contradictory situation. As Chomsky notes (2003: 113), “Democratic states may prefer to cooperate with authoritarian regimes, especially when strategic interests are at stake.” This situation reveals the contradictions between defending democracy as a universal value and its practical implementation. Countries that believe in democracy often cooperate with authoritarian regimes in their self-interest and turn a blind eye to violations of democracy’s basic principles.

The contradictions of democracy reveal that this form of government is not perfect; however, they also reflect the potential and evolutionary power of democracy. Democracy requires a constant process of questioning, criticism, and reform. The tensions between the rule of majority and minority rights, freedom and security, and equality and economic inequalities are the challenges that democratic societies encounter. The reflection of these contradictions in constitutional texts causes democracy to develop a tense space between perception and reality. This situation is reflected as the distinction between genuine democracy and pseudo democracy. Democracy cannot be built on solid foundations without the necessary institutional and legal support, yet more importantly, it is built on the foundations of society, which means that it is not problematic in terms of social acceptance and legitimacy (Ercins, 2012: 81). The differences that societies have experienced between the written form of democracy and the actual practice lead them to experience the negative effects of this gap. Making the concept of democracy functionless or impossible in terms of implementation results in it becoming objectionable; the emerging situation can be accepted as the result of the impossibility of democracy rather than its failure (Aktan, 2023: 131). Democracy, to which almost all societies in the world ascribe inviolability, takes on a negative structure due to this predicament.

Remembering Rousseau's statement, "If the gods had a nation, it would be governed by democracy; humans cannot build such a perfect system." The emphasis on how precious and inaccessible democracy is indicates a reference to its impossibility. Some of the values that people sacrifice while implementing such a system in their own societies cause democracy to reach a dead end and eventually turn into a pseudo democracy. Although democracy is identified with a concept such as popular sovereignty, it involves making a choice among the options available in the system, prioritizing the relatively better of the options offered; this is, at best, an approach to the ideal. Direct democracy is almost a dystopia, which is another situation that distances this concept from its roots. The reasons that democracy turns into a pseudo mechanism by staying away from its roots reveals that a similar situation emerges, proposed by the principle of Arrow's Impossibility Theorem, in which a mechanism is designed for a set of events and an effective (optimal) benefit is obtained in this way (Dođru, 2015: 3). In this context, democracy, as an effort to choose the best among the existing choices, moves away from its roots when the ideal is left out. Considering all these the areas where we can find forms of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy—electoral environments, freedoms of the press, individual rights, independence of the judiciary, participation of the public in elections, the supremacy of law, separation of powers, limitation of power, transparency, and accountability—are important places to examine to what extent democracy is applied in practice.

2. THE CONCEPTS OF DEMOCRACY AND DEMOCRATIZATION İN TURKISH POLITICAL LIFE

In order to survive, a person needs to fulfil basic needs such as food, shelter and clothing (Göksoy Sevinçli, 2024: 821), as well as needs that affect decision-making mechanisms such as self-fulfilment. This is realised to some extent through the right to make choices which points to democracy. Democracy, which means the rule of the people, has been included in the literature with different uses in different societies (Demir, 2010: 597). In addition The development of democracy plays an important role in strengthening political participation (Yılmaz & Mecek, 2019: 769). This concept, adopted in different ways based on the social, political, and legal situations of societies, also has different meanings according to the level of development of societies. In addition, we see that different forms of democracy have emerged in terms of the exercise of sovereignty. Examples of these different forms include (Tunç, 2008: 1116). The concept of democracy comes from the Greek words "demos," meaning "people," and "kratein," meaning "sovereignty" and "rule" (Parry & Moran, 1994: 1-2). Thus, democracy is etymologically defined as "sovereignty of the people" or, in the words of A. Lincoln, "government of the people, by the people, for the people" (Sartori, 1993: 36). This definition emphasizes normative and ideal democracy, and yet this perspective has its own issues. The fact that the control mechanism is problematic can turn the situation into an unmanageable condition. According to Plato, the first thinker who systematically reflected on democracy, democracy is the least good political order because it can easily turn into ochlocracy (rule of the masses), which is a deviation of democracy and thus leads to tyranny, the worst political order (Kuçuradi, 1998: 21). Therefore, the functioning of democracy depends on its having a smooth control mechanism and preventing it from turning into a mass oppression. We have already emphasized that there are some contradictions in A. Lincoln's definition of democracy. First, the concept of "the people" bears nonidentical segments with different interest groups. Second, an expression of expectation is emphasized in "for the people"; this concept does not coincide, however, with the term "people" in general, and the term "for" points to the existence of those who are in a position to benefit from the situation. Finally, in today's conditions, it is seen that the situation expressed by the concept of "government by the people," which is accepted as the sine qua non of direct democracy, is not possible in practice due to geographical and physical conditions and the emergence of crowded communities; thus the applicability of this form of democracy becomes almost impossible (Özdemir, 2018: 18). Popper (1945) defines democracy as an "open society" and sees it as a tool to guide people toward a better future. According to him, however, democracy is not an ideal system but a structure that needs to be constantly criticized and improved. In addition, democracy offers a mechanism to control the mistakes and mismanagement of those in power, but it is not a perfect form of government. This chaotic structure endeavors to build a society close to the ideal by establishing its own control mechanism. In fact, achieving social equality in real terms is a dream (Heywood, 2015: 93). This points to another dilemma for democracy.

The implementation of the idea of democracy is handled within the framework of a process defined as "democratization". This process—which is defined as a safe harbor to arrive at the end of an authoritarian or totalitarian understanding and the evolution into an ideal state through continuous change, transformation, and renewal—has become one of the most popular concepts of today (Catt, 1999; 2002; Garrard et al., 2000; Whitehead). Today, as a consequence of witnessing various forms of democracy to which societies adhere to

avoid oppressive regimes, one might characterize the process up to the point of discovering the ideal as democratization. In fact, this process can also be considered the stage of the formation of the political culture of states and societies. Transition to democracy is the process of gradually trying all forms of democracy, experiencing the process of democratization and the formation of political culture.

Political culture entered the literature of political science as a theory with the study “The Civic Culture” conducted by Gabriel A. Almond and Sidney Verba. This work was published in 1963 and aroused great interest. The researchers extensively examined the political structures of the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany in this study (Çalışkan, 2016: 24). Their theory attracted great attention in a short time and became an indispensable method to explain political change and transformation models. Some developments in the following years caused this popularity to gradually weaken. In particular, the predominance of theories such as “Dependency Theory” and “Rational Choice Theory” led to a decline in interest in political culture (Pye, 1991: 505). The value of a focus on political culture receded when the “The Civic Culture” was subjected to serious criticism. The understanding that democracy can serve its purpose if it guarantees not only political participation but also equality, freedom, and individual rights (Dahl, 1971: 15) is one of the bases of these criticisms.

Political culture is the product of an understanding that is different from other social science concepts. Much as it is difficult for social scientists to reach a consensus on a subject, political culture is one of the exceptions because social scientists tend to agree on this issue (Erden, 2023: 168). Today, one could argue that there is a broad consensus in both state and society that this concept has been fully realized (Welch, 2013: 1). Like a living organism, political culture is shaped in social life and is formed in search of the ideal, which allows society and the state mechanism to establish consensus on it. It should be emphasized that political culture has an extremely critical importance in the functioning of a political system. Political culture, however, is also sometimes wrongly used due to different theoretical perspectives on it and its indiscriminate use in academic language. Various features of political life, from political prejudices to political style, from political mood to what is and is not considered legitimate, are considered within the scope of this concept (Gencer, 2002: 219). To give a few examples for a full understanding of political culture conceptually, “Political culture is a set of norms and values that help people make sense of the problematic political reality and guide their behavior, thus ensuring the continuity of political-social life through a common consciousness among members of society” (Geertz, 1973: 220). Almond, who is considered the pioneer of the concept of political culture, defines political culture as a “cognitive map” that helps people make sense of the socioeconomic environment they live in (Gencer, 2002: 220). In a broad sense, political culture can be defined as attitudes and behaviors about how economic and political life should be conducted.

When considering the political codes of Turkish society, one must consider that Turkish political culture has a rich history. Turks have been interacting with many societies since they emerged on the stage of history: they began in Central Asia, regarded Anatolia as a homeland, adopted Islam, founded the Ottoman state, and passed into Republican Turkey (Yolcu, 2019: 99). Belief in God lies at the root of Turks’ political culture. Thus, religion constitutes the source of legitimacy of political culture. In Western countries, we see a mechanism of political culture based on class distinction; when we look at the basis of Ottoman political culture, however, one encounters a ruler-governed structure (İnalçık, 1990: 31). The members of the first group, the rulers, were servants to the sultan, while the members of the second group, the ruled, could be defined as absolute rulers (Mardin, 1997: 168). An examination of the history of democracy in the republican era reveals a dual distinction from the founding of the republic until the 1960s, one of which is the statist elitists who advocated a statist understanding, and the other is the traditionalist conservatives who opposed the first group in political and economic terms and can even be described as the result of a reaction to the first group (Niray & Deniz, 2009: 72). We can argue that this dual understanding has been in conflict in certain areas throughout the history of the republican period. Despite this conflict, it is possible to claim that a democratic political culture has finally been established, even though it has taken many years. Especially since 1960, although six direct or indirect military coups were negative steps for the sake of the establishment of democracy and political culture, the society has embraced democratic methods more firmly each time, which has led to the establishment of an important tradition for democratization (Okur Çakıcı, 2016: 11). The military forces’ habit of intervening in the political system greatly damages the development of democracy. Military interventions, which stand as the most serious threat to democracy, have led to the establishment of democratic habits contrary to expectations as a result of the people’s struggle against this situation.

The deviation of some concepts from their intended purpose and the use of the army, citizenship, and military service outside of their original meaning have caused the political culture to vary from time to time in Turkey. This situation has led to the emergence of both a political understanding of the state and an economic ideological understanding of the state (Görmez, 1999: 17). The state has been sacralized as an ideological and cultural structure rather than a political structure, and thus, it took time for the culture of democracy to settle. Other challenges in the establishment of a culture of democracy in Turkey are the distancing and even obstruction of different ideas by the ruling power and the low resilience of democratic mechanisms to overcome adversity (Kongar, 2016: 15). The fact that those who come to power do not tolerate differences, that the mechanisms seen as the guarantee of democratic life during coup periods appear weak in resisting coups, and that political representation is often weak in the face of difficulties have led to negative situations in the consolidation of democracy (Kalaycıoğlu, 2008: 4). The consolidation and democratization of political culture in Turkey has periodically been possible with the condition of resisting military and political elites. The efforts of politicians to remain in power after they have come to power have sometimes encountered obstruction by the bureaucratic elites, and many ruling parties could not overcome this situation.

3. DEMOCRATIZATION PROCESS IN TURKEY: LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL PERSPECTIVES

It is necessary to mention the polyarchy concept developed by R. A. Dahl, who made important observations on democratization processes. Polyarchy, which is used in the sense of the rule of the many, was first used by Dahl in 1953 to talk about representative democracy. Dahl's emphasis has been described as the rule of the many, unlike monarchy, aristocracy, and oligarchy. He emphasizes that a wave similar to democratization is embodied in polyarchy. The first of these waves was the period between 1776 and 1930, which emerged with the US and French revolutions and in which the number of many countries with polyarchic institutions increased. The second period was between 1950 and 1959, when the number of countries governed by polyarchy increased. The third period is the democratization process with polyarchy in Latin American countries after 1980 (Dahl, 1989: 299). Huntington mentions three waves of democratization processes and emphasizes that these waves created three reverse waves: in the face of the first wave between 1828 and 1926, the first reverse wave took place between 1922 and 1942; in the second wave between 1943 and 1962, the second reverse wave occurred between 1958 and 1975. The third wave of democratization began in 1974, when democratization movements in Portugal, Spain, and Greece were followed by political transformations in Eastern Europe in the late 1980s and then in Africa, which continued in the post-Soviet period (Aksu, 2018: 5952). The transition of the Baltic states to multiparty systems in early 1990 indicates a partial reverse wave. Communism collapsed in Poland, East Germany, Czechoslovakia, and Romania, which can also be expressed as a reverse wave (Fendoğlu, 2000: 90). Although democratization continues its third wave as a process, the examples given above show that some small reverse waves have been experienced.

It is apparent that democracy in Turkey is based on historical foundations that have been built on the idea of freedom (Karpas, 2017: 17). The most obvious form of this freedom is found in individual rights and freedoms. From this point of view, democratization of institutions in Turkey should be sought in the constitution and in multiparty life. Considering the democratization process in Turkey from the early years of the republic to the present day, if a legal and institutional framework is to be drawn, the primary focus will be on constitutional amendments, electoral systems, and supraparty reforms. When we focus on the extent to which constitutional and institutional structures have been democratized in this process and the extent to which the public has adopted these structures, constitutional and electoral system reforms—both genuine and pseudo democratization processes—can be better understood. It should be emphasized that democracy and constitutional movements follow a parallel course of development; constitutional reforms are the pioneering element of the democratization of societies. Constitutional movements have opened the door to democracy in Turkey. The answer to the question of whether constitutional texts have contributed to genuine or pseudo democracy will be possible by analyzing those prepared in the historical process. To examine the Ottoman-Turkish constitutional movements, the *Sened-i İttifak* (Charter of Alliance) should be accepted as a milestone; one must start by examining this treaty signed in 1808. This document was mutually signed by the viziers and the sultan, emphasizing that a fair attitude would be displayed in mutual governance. The taxes set by the sultan would be determined within the limits of justice, and the viziers would collect them fairly. The sultan and the viziers promised to fulfill several mutual responsibilities with this deed (Zurcher, 2016: 53). This document is valuable in that it was an attempt to prepare a legal basis for the Ottoman state structure. Although it was not in accordance with the Ottoman state tradition and the sultan was not eager to give consent, the *Sened-i İttifak*, albeit not establishing popular sovereignty, was a valuable document in terms of limiting the authority of the

sultan and preparing the ground for the Tanzimat (Reorganization) period (Ercoşkun, 2020: 49). The fact that citizens are excluded from the process demonstrates that this document is an effort of pseudo democratization rather than a real effort in terms of its contribution to the democratization process. In the process that followed the Sened-i İttifak, the Tanzimat period began, which expressed a total transformation in Turkish political, administrative, and economic life (Aktel, 1998: 177). Tanzimat refers to the period from the proclamation of the Gülhane Hatt-ı Hümayun (Rescript of Gülhane) on November 3, 1839, to the Kanun-i Esasi (Basic Law) dated 1876 (Eryılmaz, 1992: 91). The Islahat Fermanı (Reform Edict), like the Tanzimat Fermanı (Tanzimat Edict), is an important introduction to Turkish constitutions in terms of the principles it set forth, and because it was a constitutional document, it should be considered a part of the chain of Turkish constitutional documents (Gümüş, 2008: 234). The process, which meant reorganization and order in the Ottoman institutions, can also be characterized as the process of designing the institutions according to the modern era. Liberalism and Nationalism that emerged from the French Revolution had a profound effect on the imperial society, and when the Industrial Revolution emerged, the imperial administration tried to carry out some reforms in order to prevent the disintegration of the state (Bülbül, 1989: 159). The Tanzimat Fermanı and the subsequent Islahat Fermanı were efforts to transform society in social, political, economic, and legal terms. Some rights were granted to minorities with the Islahat Fermanı, and these rights were approved by the sultan. With the Islahat Fermanı, Christians and other non-Muslim populations were granted the freedom to choose their religion and sect and the right to freely perform their religious rituals. The sultan declared that Christians and other non-Muslim populations would not be subjected to any harassment, distress, or persecution while performing their worship. No one was forced to change their religion or sect (Özhazinedar, 2023: 763). Initially, this edict imposed equality in Ottoman social life (Türköne, 1995: 164); some segments of society did not like this equality, however. For example, Muslims did not want to be on equal terms with non-Muslims, and similarly, Christians did not want to be on equal terms with Jews. The Islahat Fermanı, which aimed to establish a concept of Ottomanism (Gümüş, 2008: 231), did not yield the desired results in practice due to the concerns of Muslims and non-Muslims within the empire. Thus, like the Tanzimat Fermanı, the Islahat Fermanı served as an instrument of pseudo democratization; in other words, the rights introduced in the constitutional text could not be put into practice. The intellectual preparers of the Kanun-i Esasi, declared on December 23, 1876, had begun to show their presence about 10 years earlier through the New Ottoman Association (Güner Özden, 2020: 327). This association had the idea that modern Western-style institutions would save the state from the present conflicting situation. Kanun-i Esasi was basically declared to save the state from political, military, administrative, and economic deadlock and, at the same time, to refrain from the pressure exerted by foreign states on the Ottoman state. Contemporary Western states were used as an example while doing so, which meant the modernization of society, and the most important example of this modernization in legal texts until that period was the Kanun-i Esasi (Unal Açıkgöz, 2021: 63).

The Kanun-i Esasi, regarded as the effort of the Ottoman intellectual class to transform Ottoman social life according to Western societies and as an imposition of the West on behalf of minorities, eventually removed the rights that were attempted to be secured by law, especially the functioning of the parliament, and the law was put aside. This demonstrated that genuine democratization efforts remained in written constitutional texts while different ideas were imposed in social life. The rights promised by this law were voiced and eventually put into practice in the following years. The Grand National Assembly with extraordinary powers was established in Ankara on April 23, 1920, with two unprecedented elections. A dual constitutional order was adopted with the implementation of the Law on the Organization of the Constitution and the Kanun-i Esasi, which were adopted by the Grand National Assembly on January 20, 1921. More precisely, it would be accurate to mention a dual structure that includes the noncontradictory provisions of the Kanun-i Esasi (Yamaç, 2020: 204). The 1921 Constitution envisaged a parliamentary government system in which the absolute supremacy of the legislature was seen, and although it was a short constitution both in terms of period and text, it was an important transitional constitution in terms of making radical decisions in a troubled period. The 1921 Constitution can be characterized as the only constitution that is problem free in terms of legitimacy and stakeholders because it was enacted by the parliament struggling for independence under extraordinary conditions (Can, 2021: 127).

The 1921 Constitution did not include regulations in some areas, which led to the belief that it was intended to be in force along with the Kanun-i Esasi. The judiciary, fundamental rights, presidency, and unlimited power are indicative of this situation (Gözler, 2017: 69). In addition, the fact that the Kanun-i Esasi was not repealed played a role in such an understanding. Therefore, the 1921 Constitution is important in the history of Turkish constitutionalism as it was the most democratic and the most acceptable constitutional document in terms of legitimacy. It can be argued that it complied with the principles of genuine democracy rather than pseudo

democracy. It is also an important text in terms of discussing all social issues in the parliament because the members of parliament represented all segments of society. The 1921 parliament that created the 1921 Constitution had a pluralist, participatory, and autonomous structure, which gives an idea of the legitimacy of the constitution. The 1921 Constitution is a text that should also be considered because it did not include fundamental rights and freedoms; on the other hand, the later 1924 Constitution included them. The later constitution is one of the interesting texts in terms of guaranteeing these rights, while there were differences that emerged in practice (Küçük, 2016: 6).

The 1924 Constitution, the first constitution of the republic, was Law No. 491, dated April 20, 1924 (Doğan, 2022: 815). The constitution remained in force until the May 27, 1960 coup, and although it contained important democratic articles on fundamental rights and freedoms, it was extremely weak in practice. Amendments could not be made to the 1924 Constitution, which was also an important document in terms of the transition from assembly government system to a parliamentary system. Its principles, such as stating that the country's form of government was a republic and emphasizing that sovereignty belonged unconditionally to the nation, can be shown among its prominent features. One of the most important features of the 1924 Constitution was that the principle of strict concentration of powers in the parliament during the War of Independence was transformed into a loose and mild form in 1924 (Anayurt, 1997: 682). The 1924 Constitution can also be considered as a text in which steps independent of the content of the constitution were taken in practice. As a requirement of the establishment of the Atatürk revolutions and the political atmosphere of the period (during the single-party period), the executive branch—that is, the government and the president—most of the time dominated the parliament through party discipline and party mechanism. Almost the entire parliament was composed of deputies from a political party during the single-party period (Anayurt, 1997: 690). Based on this reality, it is possible to say that the 1924 Constitution had democratic qualities not in essence but in practice. With the proclamation of the republic, important steps were taken toward modernization and Westernization under the leadership of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk. However, Atatürk's reforms limited the democratization process within the framework of single-party rule. The transition to multiparty rule in 1950 caused the Turkish democracy to enter a new phase. With the Democrat Party coming to power in this period, concepts such as political pluralism and freedom of expression came to the agenda (Lewis, 2002). This process was interrupted during the period of military coups. The process following the May 27, 1960, coup required a new beginning in the history of Turkish constitutionalism. The 38 members of the National Unity Committee (NUC) authorized a committee of professors chaired by Sıddık Sami Onar to draft a new constitution with Communiqué No. 13, dated May 28, 1960. There were two preliminary drafts of the constitution during the drafting process of the 1961 Constitution. The first of these was the "Istanbul Preliminary Draft" created under the chairmanship of Sıddık Sami Onar, and the second was the "Ankara Preliminary Draft" shared with the public by Ankara University Faculty of Political Sciences (Özkul, 2023: 21). The House of Representatives elected the Constitutional Commission on January 6, 1961, and subsequently, work on the creation of the new constitution began de facto. The draft prepared by the Scientific Committee chaired by Sıddık Sami Onar was accepted as the "study document," and the draft prepared by the Faculty of Political Sciences was accepted as the "auxiliary text" (Tunç, 2020: 669). The text prepared by the Council of Representatives and the NUC was discussed in detail, and although there was a disagreement on 17 articles, this disagreement was resolved with a new regulation, and the new constitution was accepted on May 27, 1961, on the anniversary of the coup. The new constitution was adopted with over 80% participation and 61.5% yes votes in the July 9, 1961 referendum. This constitution, which is generally stated to be a reaction to the 1924 Constitution, is argued to be strong in terms of legitimacy due to the fact that it was submitted to a popular vote and adopted. The new constitution, created as a reaction to the 1924 Constitution, aimed to reestablish Turkey's legal and institutional foundation by addressing various issues in detail within a broad text (Karademir & Tok, 2023: 68). The 1961 Constitution can be said to aim to "balance the balance" of the founding ideology of the republic by redesigning the society rather than the will of the people (Karademir and Tok, 2023: 72). Large segments of society were not included in the constitution-making process, which can be argued to reflect the constitutional understanding of pseudo democracy rather than genuine democracy in terms of democratic qualities.

4. EVALUATION OF THE POST-1980 PERIOD IN TERMS OF GENUINE DEMOCRACY AND PSEUDO DEMOCRACY

In Turkey, where the republican administration is governed within the framework of the constitutional order, it is observed that the bureaucratic functioning is often overbearing, and the decisions of the appointed, despite the people, cause some difficulties to both the elected and the people (Atmaca & Günay, 2020: 208). The transition to multiparty life can be regarded as a turning point in the transition to democratic order. However, the democratic networks that were not institutionalized immediately after this process led to three military interventions in the next 50 years. Turkish democracy, which regarded military coups as a remedy to get out of crisis periods, faced a return to an authoritarian structure after each coup. The coup of May 27, 1960, led to the 1961 Constitution, and the mistakes made in the constitution-making process were almost a precursor to the subsequent coups (Dursun, 2005: 175). The political, social, and economic transformation brought about by the May 27 coup led to new problems in the organizational structure of state organizations (Keskin, 2020: 1). The creation of the 1961 Constitution led to student upheavals and a reaction among the working class beginning in the mid-1960s. An increase in domestic problems and the intensification of terrorism and anarchy in Turkey before 1980 proved the inadequacy of the 1961 Constitution (Dursun, 2008: 422). Turkey needed to escape from crisis; the inadequacy of democratic methods and processes to overcome this predicament made military intervention almost inevitable, and finally, on September 12, 1980, the Turkish Armed Forces (TAF) seized power on command (Dursun, 2005: 177). In fact, this is the way of solving crises in societies where democratic institutions have not been developed and the culture of democracy has not been fully established. The method of overcoming problems through the use of force had made military coups inevitable, and this method, which almost had become traditional, reappeared in the 1980 coup. Following the TAF seizure of power on the basis of their duty to “protect and safeguard the Republic of Turkey,” the need for a new constitution emerged (Toprak, 2020: 178). The blockages in politics before 1980, the weakness of the executive branch, and the increase in anarchy led to the need for a new constitution. Following the coup, work on the new constitution began without delay.

The process officially started on November 1, 1980; a constituent assembly was formed for the purpose of creating the constitution and the National Security Council (NSC), and the constituent assembly would manage the process until the constitution was submitted to a popular vote. The NSC strictly forbade any discussion of the provisional provisions of the constitution and declared this in a declaration. Discussion of the provisional articles of the constitution was strictly forbidden. The provisional provisions were highly controversial both in terms of human rights and democracy. For example, Kenan Evren was elected as president for seven years with the constitutional referendum; the members of the NSC formed the Presidential Council, and political party leaders and executives were prohibited from engaging in any kind of politics for 10 years (Toprak, 2020: 178). In addition to the fact that there was no criticism of the declaration in the press, the TAF was the sole determining element in the formation of the 1982 Constitution, and the task of constitution making was undertaken by a five-person military committee on behalf of the TAF (Tanör, 1994: 114). The general framework of the 1982 Constitution was already determined by the “law on constitutional order” adopted immediately after the coup. The text of the new constitution was drafted in line with this law.

The society, which was condemned to a text that was not stable, could not object to the new constitution, and the signal that it would be far from a democratic structure was clear from the outset. The chairman of the Constitutional Commission accepted the constitution, saying, “Our greatest difficulty at the moment is to draft a democratic constitution in an undemocratic environment” (Cumhuriyet, May 9, 1982). This outlook, offered during the drafting phase of the constitution, made it almost impossible to yield a reliable text. This contradiction between the constitutional text and practice constituted the core of the subject of this study. When we look at the 1982 Constitution from the perspective of genuine democracy versus pseudo democracy, we see that although it claims to be a document that grounds the democratic structure in Turkey, some of the principles put forward in the name of institutionalizing democracy render democracy dysfunctional in practice. These principles can often be regarded as limiting freedoms, excessively strengthening executive power, or weakening democratic oversight mechanisms. Some democratic principles have, at times, not been fully achieved in practice or have become dysfunctional. Some basic democratic principles placed in the constitution have, for various reasons, been minimally implemented or not at all. In countries where the rule of law prevails, the independence of the judiciary is constitutionally guaranteed as one of the fundamental principles.

Article 9 of the 1982 Constitution states that “judicial power is exercised by independent courts on behalf of the Turkish nation.” Similarly, Article 138 of the Constitution states that “judges are independent in their duties;

they judge according to their conscientious convictions in accordance with the Constitution, the law, and the law.” This was arranged as in the 1961 Constitution (Zafer, 1988: 432). Article 141 of the constitution emphasizes the transparency and reliability of the judiciary by stating that court hearings are open to all. Nevertheless, in practice, the full independence of the judiciary is questioned from time to time; the existence of certain failures in judicial oversight and the acceptance of judicial decisions on citizens’ minds make this area questionable. Although the constitution enshrines the rule of law and the principle of equal and fair justice for all, it cannot be said that the rule of law is fully operational in practice.

Moreover, the rule of law may not be the expression of a meaningful and valuable situation; Marxist ideology argues that law serves the interests of the ruling class and that in class societies, there is one thing that is more important than freedom and equality of everyone—the interests of the ruling class—and the rules of law are the guarantees of these interests (Uygun, 2022: 540). This perspective highlights that the independence and impartiality of the judiciary is not the case for all societies. We can talk about genuine democracy as long as the independence and impartiality of the judiciary that are guaranteed constitutionally are transparent and accountable and the rule of law does not serve the interests of elites. Although the constitution recognizes the right of political parties to operate freely, in practice, some parties are shut down, face pressure, or are prevented from participating in elections. To be able to discuss the existence of democratic governance in a country, it is necessary for opposition to political power to be recognized as a right, different social segments must be able to live together, and the rights of those who are not in power must be guaranteed (Öztürk & Sümer, 2021: 1327). It is also against the basic principles of the rule of law for political parties to engage in any kind of action. According to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), in order for the dissolution of political parties not to be contrary to the ECHR, the reason for dissolution must be stipulated in the constitution or the law, the dissolution of a party must be based on one of the legitimate aims set out in the second paragraph of Article 11, and the intervention must be necessary for democratic societies (Öztürk & Sümer, 2021: 1331). If these conditions are met, valid grounds for the dissolution of political parties will have emerged. Otherwise, putting an end to the activities of political parties, which are indispensable elements of political life with a democratic purpose, will create problems. One area that demonstrates whether democracy is genuine or pseudo is whether elections are free and equal. Although free and equal elections are stated in the constitution, there are debates about how free and equal elections are in reality.

The principle of free elections means that citizens who have the right to vote should be able to vote without any pressure or coercion (Sezer, 2021: 287). However, the use of public resources during the election process and the state’s intervention in the elections determine the democratic character of the elections in the case of equal elections. Freedom of expression is one of the most fundamental rights of human beings and perhaps the most valuable one (Teziç, 1990: 32). Although the constitution guarantees this right under Article 26, this freedom can be restricted in some cases in practice. Freedom of expression allows a person to develop his or her material and spiritual existence; taking away this right means that the person is unable to express himself or herself and is materially and spiritually worn out (Kaboğlu, 2000: 107). In particular, punitive sanctions on freedom of expression can lead politicians, activists, and journalists to a dead end. This results in incomplete implementation of the principle of freedom of expression. The freedom of expression is subject to restrictions under Article 26/2 of the Constitution, which leads to the emergence of arbitrary practices. This article may be restricted for the purposes of “national security, public order, public safety, the protection of the fundamental characteristics of the republic and the indivisible integrity of the State with its territory and nation, the prevention of crimes, the punishment of criminals, the non-disclosure of information duly designated as a state secret, the protection of the reputation or rights, private and family lives, or professional secrets prescribed by law, or the proper fulfillment of judicial duty” (Kula, 2021: 559). This wording of the relevant article appears as a reservation to freedom of expression.

The right to meetings and demonstration marches, which is specified in the constitution, can also be evaluated within this framework. This right addressed in Article 34 of the Constitution can be stated as another form of the freedom of expression specified in Articles 25 and 26 of the Constitution (Ekinci, 2019: 756). Article 2 of Law No. 2911 on Meetings and Demonstration Marches describes these activities. Although stated as a constitutional right, these rights are sometimes restricted, especially for opposition groups and protesters. The right to demonstrations can be restricted on security grounds or because social peace will be harmed. Although this right is also inherent in the constitution, it is sometimes arbitrarily restricted, turning it into a so-called right. Fundamental rights and freedoms are guaranteed in Articles 2 and 12 of the Constitution, yet this is sometimes restricted to the detriment of the individual. All these rights guaranteed in constitutional texts can be restricted to

the detriment of the individual for different reasons. This gives rise to the debate around genuine democracy and pseudo democracy. Although the 1982 Constitution guarantees many democratic principles, normative concepts such as freedom, equality, justice, and rights are rendered meaningless and disregarded under certain circumstances and conditions (Heywood, 2017: 14). This situation has been partially improved through constitutional amendments over time; in order for them to be fully realized, there is a need for a pluralist and civilian constitution in which all segments of society will be involved, starting from the drafting process, leading to a consensus text that will not have the slightest hesitation in terms of legitimacy.

5. CONCLUSION AND EVALUATION

A dialogue between Otañes, Megabyzus, and Darius on political regimes in one of the chapters of Herodotus' famous "History" addresses the government in a division of monarchy, oligarchy, and democracy. Herein, monarchy, oligarchy, and democracy are analyzed separately, and in the end, it is seen that there is a consensus that democracy is the rule of the rabble of the masses of the people (Tunçay, 2015: 4). Corporate reputation and its effective management constitute the most important agenda item for today's organisations (İzci, Atmaca & Yılmaz, 2019: 303), the measure of reputation in a state governed by the rule of law should be sought in its democratic nature. In his speech in the British House of Commons in 1947, Churchill drew attention to the negativity of democracy by saying, "Democracy is the worst form of government if we exclude other forms of government that have been tried from time to time" (Heywood, 2006: 95). Joseph Schumpeter sees democracy as a form of government in which people ignore long-term stability in favor of short-term interests (Schumpeter, 2003: 269). negates democracy on the grounds that it produces leaders who come to power by popular vote but neglect the interests of the people in the long run. One of the negative aspects of democracy is the criticism that it will cause significant economic inequalities. (Piketty, 2014: 42) expresses this as follows: "Economic inequality affects the functioning of democracy because the rich have disproportionate power in the decision-making mechanism of states." Despite these aspects, (Rousseau, 2018: 107) highlights that democracy has important virtues in designing societies, in making them consent to equal rights. (Gershman, 2011: 25) emphasizes that democracy is a unique method for resolving social conflicts and draws attention to the virtue of democracy in establishing dialogue between different groups. In contrast to Piketty, Amartya Sen notes that democracy promotes economic development and produces policies to improve the quality of life of individuals, which is extremely important for social life. Studies conducted on democracy should be analyzed by considering these aspects. This study focused on the ideal of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy regardless of the positive and negative aspects of democracy. The study especially focused on the functioning of democracy in the constitutional text and in practice and gave examples from the history of Turkish democracy in the specified period. Considered the twenty-first-century's value-laden concept, democracy, which is the guarantee of individual rights and freedoms, has encountered several positive and negative judgments, as mentioned above.

Democracy is the ideal form of government of today's societies and perhaps the best form of government to be achieved. It also includes contradictions between what it promises and what it implements. This contradictory situation leads to the emergence of the concepts of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy. It can be argued that there is a positive relationship between constitutions and the development of democracy. Securing individual rights and freedoms through constitutional texts is critical for democracy. In this respect, the development of written constitutions also enables the establishment and stabilization of democracy in all its aspects. The distinction between genuine democracy and pseudo democracy is manifested in the fact that some rights and freedoms guaranteed in constitutional texts are ignored in practice, or these rights are restricted on certain grounds. This study discussed the history of Turkish democracy and focused on examples that can be evaluated within the framework of the principle of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy. Examples of these types of democracy can be found especially in constitutions that were created in the periods of military coups.

The post-1980 period was taken as the research area of the subject in the study and it was determined that several rights and freedoms were easily neglected in practice in the antidemocratic environment that emerged following the September 12, 1980 coup. In the process leading to the 1982 Constitution, nondemocratic elements starting from the constitution-making stage led to a process in which some rights and freedoms that were legally guaranteed after the adoption of the constitution encountered deficiencies in practice. The constitutional documents created by the oppressive and authoritarian governments of the coup processes in line with their own wishes somehow hinder freedoms with extremely undemocratic elements in the implementation phase. There are a number of rights and freedoms that are in the essence of the constitution but are not included or are restricted in practice, which is called pseudo democracy.

Elections, individual rights and freedoms, independence of the judiciary, duties and powers of the head of state, and freedom of expression can be listed as the areas where the most contradictory situation emerged after 1980 in the name of genuine democracy and pseudo democracy. In Turkey, the antidemocratic environment after 1980 and the constitution created by the military coup led to a deepening of this separation. Democratic societies, in the development of fundamental rights and freedoms, first put forward a qualified and inclusive civilian constitutional text. Thus, democracy can be regarded as an important step in the advancement of democracy and human rights in Turkey. Yet it is also important to have a majoritarian, civilian constitution with a high level of social participation in all subsequent stages, starting from the drafting process. Such a constitutional text will not only guarantee a text that does not need to be amended repeatedly, as in previous examples, but will also enable all rights and freedoms guaranteed by law to be realized in practice. Therefore, an important mechanism in the distinction between genuine democracy and pseudo democracy will be possible with a free, democratic, and legitimately unquestionable constitution made by the people, for the people.

REFERENCES

- Aksu, H. (2018). Demokratikleşme Ve Türkiye’de Demokratikleşme Sürecinde Karşılaşılan Temel Sorunlar. *Social Sciences Studies Journal*, 4(27), 5949-5958.
- Aktan, C. C. (2023). Demokrasi ve Kakistokrasi, Demokrasi’ye 10 Eleştiri: Demokrasi Neden İyi Bir Rejim Değildir?. *Hukuk ve İktisat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 15(2), 130-145.
- Aktel, M. (1998). Tanzimat Fermanı’nın Toplumsal Yansıması. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 3, 177-184.
- Anayurt, Ö. (1997). 1924 Anayasası’nda Meclis-Yürütme İlişkileri. *Atatürk Araştırma Merkezi Dergisi*, 8(39), 673-94.
- Atmaca, Y. & Günay, M. C. (2020). Bürokratik Oligarşi: Türk Kamu Yönetimi Ekseninde Bir Analiz. *R&SResearch Studies Anatolia Journal*, 3 (3), 199-210.
- Bülbül, G. (1989). Islahat Fermanı’nı Hazırlayan Sebepler ve Islahat Fermanı. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2(2), 157-179.
- Can, O. (2021). 1921 Anayasası’nın 100. Yılı: Bir İstisnai Başarı ve Dramatik Başarısızlık Hikâyesi. *Anayasa Yargısı Dergisi*, 38(1), 127-170.
- Catt, H. (1999). *Democracy in Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Chomsky, N. (2003). *Hegemony or Survival: America’s quest for Global Dominance*. New York: Metropolitan Books.
- Cumhuriyet Gazetesi, 9 Mayıs 1982.
- Çalışkan, K. (2016). Siyasal Kültür: Yeni Yaklaşımlara Genel Bir Bakış. *Marmara Üniversitesi Siyasal Bilimler Dergisi*, 4(2), 23-46.
- Dahl, R. A. (1971). *Polyarchy: Participation and Opposition*. London: Yale University Press.
- Dahl, R. A. (1989). *Demokrasi ve Eleştirileri*. Ankara: Yetkin Yayınları.
- Demir, N. (2010). Demokrasinin Temel İlkeleri ve Modern Demokrasi Kuramları. *Ege Akademik Bakış*, 10(2), 597-611.
- Doğan, K. C. (2022). Cumhuriyet Tarihimizin İlk Anayasası Olarak 1924 Anayasası’nın Genel Olarak Değerlendirilmesi. *Sosyal, Beşeri ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 5(6), 813-824.
- Doğru, B. (2015). Arrow’un Tercihlerde İmkânsızlık Teoremi İle Kafkasya’daki Sorunlara Bakış. *Hukuk ve İktisat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(1), 1-10.
- Dursun, D. (2005). Türk Demokrasisinde Kurumsallaşma Sorunu ve Krizleri Çözme Yöntemi Olarak Askerî Darbeler. *Muhafazakâr Düşünce*, 3, 175-197.
- Dursun, S. (2008). Türkiye’nin Güvenlik Algılamasındaki Değişim: 12 Eylül 1980 Askeri Müdahalesi Sonrası Dönem. *Çağdaş Türkiye Tarihi Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(16-17), 421-433.

- Ekinci, B. E. (2019) Toplantı Ve Gösteri Yürüyüşü Düzenleme Hakkı Bakımından Bildirim Usûlünün Kapsamı. Ankara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi, 68(4), 753-94.
- Ercoskun, B. (2020). Türkiye'nin Demokratikleşme Sürecindeki Parametreleri. *Lectio Socialis*, 4(1), 41-58.
- Ercins, G. (2012). Türkiye'nin Demokratikleşmesinde Toplumsal Sorun Alanları. *Gazi Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 14(1), 79-102.
- Erden, Ö. O. (2023). Türkiye'de Siyasal Kültür: Temel Bir Demokrasi Meselesi. *Memleket Siyaset Yönetim*, 18(39), 166-193.
- Eryılmaz, B. (1992). *Tanzimat ve Yönetimde Modernleşme*. İstanbul: İşaret Yayınları.
- Fendoğlu, T. (2000). Demokrasi, Demokratikleşme Dalgaları ve Çıkış Garantileri, "Kamu Hukuku: Anayasa Hukuku" Başlığı altında yer almaktadır. "Prof. Dr. Seyfullah Edis'e armağan" kitabından alınmıştır. ss. 79-93.
- Garrard, J./ Tolz, V./White, R.(2000), *European Democratization since 1800: Past & Present*, Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- Geertz, C. (1973). *The Interpretation of Cultures*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gencer, B. (2002). Türk Siyasal Kültürü ve Ahmed Cevdet Paşa. *Uludağ Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, XXI(2), 217-238.
- Gershman, C. (2011). Democracy Promotion: A Global Perspective. *Foreign Affairs*, 90(5), 18-30.
- Göksoy Sevinçli, B. (2024). Yoksulluk Algısı ile Yaşam Memnuniyeti Arasındaki İlişkiye Yönelik Bir Araştırma: Bitlis Örneği. *İDEALKENT*, 15(42), 816-843.
- Görmez, K. (1999). Türkiye'de Siyasal Yapı ve Siyasal Kültür. *Gazi Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1(1), 13-18.
- Gözler, K. (2017). *Türk Anayasa Hukuku*. 2. Bası, Bursa: Ekin Yayınevi.
- Gümüş, M. (2008). Anayasal Meşrûti Yönetime Medhal: 1856 Islahat Fermanı'nın Tam Metin İncelemesi. *BİLİG*, 47, 215-240.
- Güner Özden, S. (2020). I. Meşrutiyet'e Giden Yol: 1876 Senesine Yeniden Bakmak. *Uluslararası Tarih ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 23, 323-360.
- Heywood, A. (2017). *Siyaset Teorisine Giriş*, Terc; Köse, H. M., 8. Baskı. İstanbul: Küre Yayınları.
- Heywood, A. (2015). *Siyasi İdeolojiler*, Çev; Bayram, A. K., 9. Baskı. Ankara: Adres Yayınları.
- Heywood, A. (2006). *Siyaset*, Çev; Özipek, B. B. Ankara: Liberte Yayınları.
- İnalçık, H. (1990). Osmanlı toplum yapısının evrimi. Çeviren: Mehmet Özden, Fahri Unan. *Türkiye Günlüğü*, 11, 30-41.
- İzci, F. Atmaca, Y. & Yılmaz, V. (2019). Kamu Kurumlarında İtibar Yönetimi: Kurumsal İtibarı Ölçme ve Değerlendirme, *Avrasya Sosyal ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(7), 302-316.
- Jean-Jacques, R. (1982). *Toplum Sözleşmesi*. Çev, Günyol, V. İstanbul: Adam Yayıncılık.
- Kaboğlu, İ. (2000). "Düşünce Özgürlüğü", *İnsan Hakları*, (der. K. Tankuter). İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
- Kalaycıoğlu, E. (2008). Türkiye'de Demokrasinin Pekişmesi: Bir Siyasal Kültür Sorunu., Ed. Serap Yazıcı, Kemal Gözler ve Fuat Keyman), Prof. Dr. Ergun Özbudun'a Armağan: *Essays in Honor of Ergun Özbudun*, I, 247-277.
- Karadaş, A. B. (2020). Anayasalcılık ve Demokrasi Arasındaki İlişki: Sürekli Bir Çatışma Mı Simbiyotik Bir Birliktelik Mi?. *Yıldırım Beyazıt Hukuk Dergisi*, 1, 123-152.
- Karademir, A. ve Tok, N. (2023). 1961 Anayasası'nın Türk Kamu Yönetimine Etkilerinin Devlet Memurluğu Kavramı Üzerinden İncelenmesi. *Aksaray Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Meslek Yüksekokulu Dergisi*, 1(1), 65-77.

- Karpat, K. H. (2017). Türk Demokrasi Tarihi Sosyal, Kültürel, Ekonomik Temeller. 8. Baskı. İstanbul: Timaş Yayınları.
- Keskin, Y. Z. (2020). Türkiye Siyaseti ve Devlet Örgütlenmesinde 12 Mart Muhtırasının Etkileri. Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, 22(100), 1-15.
- Kestel, S. (2020). Siyasal Kültüre Yansımaları Açısından Türkiye’de Seçim Sistemleri ve İletişimi, (Doktora Tezi). İstanbul Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Kongar, E. (2016). Demokrasi ve Kültür. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi.
- Kuçuradi, İ. (1998). Yirmibirinci Yüzyılın Eşiğinde Demokrasi Kavramı ve Sorunları. Hacettepe Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi, Cumhuriyetimizin 75. Yılı Özel Sayısı, 21-27.
- Kula, A. (2021). Anayasa Mahkemesi Bireysel Başvuru Kararlarında Devlet Memurlarının İfade Özgürlüğü: Hasan Güngör, Hasan Güngör (2) ve Zeki Çınar Başvuruları. Hacettepe Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi, 11(1), 555-593.
- Küçük, A. (2016). 1924 Anayasasında Temel Hak ve Hürriyetler. Liberal Düşünce Dergisi, 82, 5-54.
- Lewis, B. (2002). The Emergence of Modern Turkey. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Mardin, Ş. (1997). Siyasal ve sosyal bilimler: Makaleler II, Der. Mümtaz’er Türköne, Tuncay Önder. 4. Baskı. İstanbul: İletişim Yayınları.
- Mill, J.S. (2001). On Liberty. Ontario: Batoche Books Limited.
- Mudde, C. (2004). The Populist Zeitgeist. Government and Opposition, 39(4), 541-563.
- Mudde, C. & Kaltwasser, C. R. (2017). Populism A very Short Introduction. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Niray, N. & Deniz, D. (2009). “Geçmişten Günümüze Türkiye’de Demokrasi ve Siyasal Kültür Paradigmaları”, Siyasal Kültür Yazıları. Der. Nasır Niray. İstanbul: Derin Yayınları.
- Okur Çakıcı, F. (2016). Osmanlı’dan Türkiye’ye Siyasal Miras: Türk Siyasal Kültürü Üzerine Bir İnceleme. The Journal of International Scientific Researches, 1(2), 8-15.
- Özdemir, G. (2018). Huntington’un Demokratikleşme Dalgaları Bağlamında Türk Demokratikleşmesine Bakış ve 15 Temmuz’un Önemi. Sakarya İktisat Dergisi, 7(1), 27-51.
- Özhazinedar, T. (2024). Tanzimat Fermanı, Islahat Fermanı, Adalet Fermanı ve Kanun-i Esasi’nin Tahlili. 21. Yüzyılda Eğitim Ve Toplum, 12(36), 759-786.
- Özkul, F. (2023). 1961 Anayasası’nın Türk Anayasacılığındaki Yeri ve Önemi. Hasan Kalyoncu Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi, 13(25), 15-61.
- Öztürk, İ., & Sümer, A. E. (2021). Siyasi Parti Kapatma Davalarının Hukuki Niteliği. İstanbul Hukuk Mecmuası, 79(4), 1323-1356.
- Parry, G & Moran, M. (1994), "Introduction: Problems of Democracy and Democratization", Democracy and Democratization (Eds. Parry, G./Moran, M.) London: Routledge, 1-2.
- Popper, K. (1945). The Open Society and Its Enemies. London: Butler & Tanner Ltd.
- Piketty, T. (2014). Capital in the Twenty-First Century. London: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Pye, L. W. (1991). Political Culture Revisited. Political Psychology, 12(3), 487-508.
- Rousseau, J. J. (2018). İnsanlar Arasındaki Eşitsizliğin Temeli ve Kökenleri, Çev; Yıldırım, E. İstanbul: Roman Yayınları.
- Sartori, G. (1993). Demokrasi Teorisine Geri Dönüş (Çev: Karamustafaoğlu, T./Turhan, M.), Ankara: Türk Demokrasi Vakfı Yayınları.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (2003). Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy. London & New York.

- Sezer, İ. E. (2021). Seçimlerin Serbestliği İlkesi Bağlamında Mektupla Oy Kullanımı. *Uyuşmazlık Mahkemesi Dergisi*, 18, 283-307.
- Tanör, B. (1994). *İki Anayasa 1961-1982*. İstanbul: Beta Yayınevi.
- Teziç, E. (1990). Türkiye’de Siyasal Düşünce ve Örgütlenme Özgürlüğü. *Anayasa Yargısı Dergisi*, 7, 31-46.
- Tocqueville, A. (2016). *Amerika’da Demokrasi*, Çev; Sertdemir Özdemir, S., İstanbul: İletişim Yayınları.
- Toprak, E. (2020). 1982 Anayasası’nın Hazırlanma Süreci. *Uluslararası Türk Dünyası Bilimsel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 1(2), 177-185.
- Türköne, M. (1995). “Islahat Fermanı”, *Osmanlı Ansiklopedisi (Tarih Medeniyet Kültür)*, C.6, İstanbul.
- Tunç, B. (2020). Türk Anayasa Tarihinde 1961 Anayasası’nın Yeri ve Önemi. *Karadeniz Araştırmaları*, 17(67), 657-692.
- Tunç, H. (2008). Demokrasi Türleri ve Müzakereci Demokrasi Kavramı. *Gazi Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, XII(1-2), 1113-1132.
- Tunçay, M. (2015). *Batı’da Siyasal Düşünceler Tarihi*, İstanbul: İstanbul Bilgi Üniversitesi Yayınları.
- Türk, H. B. (2017). Jean-Luc Nancy Düşüncesinde Demokrasi Kavramı Üzerine Genel Bir Değerlendirme. *Kaygı. Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi Fen-Edebiyat Fakültesi Felsefe Dergisi*, 29, 19-31.
- Uygun, O. (2022). Hukukun Üstünlüğü İlkesi. *Yeditepe Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, 19(3), 521-558.
- Ünal Açıkgöz, M. (2021). 1876 Tarihli Kanun-i Esasi’de Yasama-Yürütme İlişkisi. *Yasama Dergisi*, 43, 61-86.
- Üskül, M. Z. (1988). 1982 Anayasası Döneminde Yargı Bağımsızlığı ve Yargıç Teminatı Üzerine Bazı Düşünceler. *Anadolu Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6(2), 431-440.
- Welch, S. (2013). *The Theory of Political Culture*, (Oxford University Press).
- Whitehead, L. (2002). *Emerging Market Democracies: East Asia and Latin America*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Yamaç, M. (2020). Türkiye Devleti’nin ilk Anayasası 1921 Teşkilat-ı Esasiye Kanunu. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 22 (TBMM’nin 100. Yılı ve Millî İrade Özel Sayısı), 204-220.
- Yılmaz, V. & Telsaç, C. (2021). Yerel Yönetimler ve Katılım, *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 2(40), 235-254.
- Yılmaz, V. & Mecek, M. (2019). Türkiye’de Mahalle Yönetimlerinin Tarihsel Gelişimi ve Hukuki Statüsü, *İdealkent*, 27(10), 769-799.
- Yolcu, T. (2019). Türkiye’de Siyasal Kültür ve Siyasal Liderlik Anlayışının Temelleri Üzerine Genel Bir Değerlendirme. *Ömer Halisdemir Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 12 (1), 93-106.
- Zabunoğlu, G. (2017). Bir Radikal Demokrasi Teorisi Olarak müzakereci demokrasi. *Ankara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, 66(4), 795-818.
- Zurcher, E. J. (2016). *Modernleşen Türkiye'nin Tarihi*. 32.Baskı, İstanbul: İletişim Yayıncılık.